

Towards Passivity Based Nonprehensile Bimanual Manipulation of Large Objects

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Abstract—In this work a passivity based control scheme to manipulate large objects supported on planar surfaces by bimanual robots is introduced. A control input is designed to accomplish the rotation and displacement of the object to a desired pose without assuming any knowledge of the object dynamics and friction dynamics between the object and the supporting surface. Passivity arguments are used to rigorously prove its stability. The proposed method is evaluated in simulations with friction forces simulated using the elastoplastic model. Experimental results performed on a bimanual robot with two 7-dof KUKA LBR iiwa 7 arms manipulating a variety of large objects verify the theoretical results.

I. INTRODUCTION

As modern robotic systems are introduced in human environments they are required to manipulate every day human objects [1]. Objects in such environments do not comply with traditional industrial standards that offer complete knowledge of the object geometry and dynamics. Furthermore the object environment dynamics are also usually unknown. Therefore robust methods must be developed in order to successfully manipulate a large variety of objects [2], [3].

To address this issue we can draw inspiration from human object manipulation [4]. Using a wide variety of prehensile [5], [6] and non prehensile motions, humans are able to manipulate objects of various shapes, weights and materials [7]. Prehensile manipulation involves precise grasping of objects, utilizing the object geometry [8], [9] and dexterous robotic fingers [10]. The popularity of non prehensile object manipulation has risen in recent years since it offers reliable results without requiring complex finger designs, as well as robustness to unknown environments and objects [11]. Robots have been used in various applications like singulating [12], [13], pushing [14], [15] or dragging [16]. Combining prehensile and non prehensile manipulations can also lead to interesting results, as by using non prehensile manipulation actions the robot can create grasp affordances and subsequently grasp the desired object [17], [18].

For the case of large sizeable objects bimanual approaches are usually employed by both humans and robots [19], [20]. Large objects are often heavy and as robots are entering everyday human environments, they will be needed to be manipulated by low payload collaborative robots. Such robots have limited lifting capabilities, therefore a series of non

prehensile bimanual manipulation actions are required to robustly execute the desired task. Examples of everyday object manipulation is the handling of luggage and boxes. Research efforts should therefore focus on strategies for pushing, pulling, dragging, etc, where the challenges of large objects i.e. large inertia, friction, unknown dynamics, should be considered for the development of robust robotic behaviors. There are only few works addressing these challenges focusing on dual arm capturing of moving objects and transportation [21], [22] rather than non-prehensile manipulation.

Bimanual robotic systems [23] offer easier manipulation of large objects as well as redundancy through their many degrees of freedom, which can be utilized to introduce constraints and optimizations in the executed motion [24]. Many bimanual manipulation approaches have been introduced in the literature [25]–[27]. For object manipulation, the majority of bimanual robotic systems utilize machine learning algorithms to learn policies to execute the desired task [25], [28]. While learning approaches offer versatility in the range and complexity of executed tasks, they lack the guarantees provided by traditional control approaches.

In this work we design a control strategy to manipulate large objects supported by planar surfaces, by bimanual robots in order to reach a desired position and orientation. In contrast to previous works, the proposed control input is proved to achieve asymptotic convergence to the desired manipulation objective through rigorous Lyapunov like stability arguments. The proposed control strategy consists of two stages. During the first stage the object reaches the desired orientation, while during the second stage the desired position is reached while maintaining the desired orientation. In both stages, the controller ensures that the robot remains in contact with the object during the entire task execution.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We assume a rigid object lying on a planar surface with two opposing parallel sides and a bimanual robot with its two end-effectors in contact with these sides as shown in Figure 1. The object dynamic parameters (mass, inertia, center of mass) are not known but its length l , i.e. the distance of the two parallel sides, is either known or estimated by an external perception system. Let $\{W\}$ be the world frame and $\{O\}$ the object frame attached to the geometric center of the object, described by the position vector $\mathbf{p}_o = [x \ y \ z]^T$ and the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_z(\theta)$ where $\mathbf{R}_z(\cdot)$ denotes a rotation about the z axis and $x, y, z, \theta \in \mathbb{R}$. Due to the contact with the supporting plane, z will remain constant throughout the entire manipulation task. We further define $\mathbf{p}_i, i \in \{1, 2\}$ the

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Fig. 1: Bimanual robot in contact with the object

end-effector position of the i th arm in $\{W\}$. When the robot end-effectors are in contact with the object, let the position of the contact points in $\{W\}$ be c_i , which coincide with p_i in this case. We further define the position of these contact points on the object sides by $c_{oi} = c_i - p_o = \mathbf{R}^o c_i$, where ${}^o c_i = [x_{ci} \ y_{ci} \ z_{ci}]^T$ is the position of the contact in $\{O\}$. Notice that the z coordinate in c_i , c_{oi} and ${}^o c_i$ for the planar case will be constant and that $l = x_{c2} - x_{c1}$.

When in contact with the rigid object's side, the following position constraint holds:

$$p_o + c_{oi} = p_i \quad (1)$$

which can be also written as:

$$p_o + \mathbf{R}^o c_i = p_i \quad (2)$$

Differentiating (2) we get:

$$\dot{p}_o + \hat{\mathbf{R}}^o c_i + \mathbf{R}^o \dot{c}_i = \dot{p}_i \quad (3)$$

which can be written as $\dot{p}_o + \hat{\mathbf{R}} \mathbf{R}^T c_{oi} + \mathbf{R}^o \dot{c}_i = \dot{p}_i$. Thus we get:

$$\dot{p}_o + \omega(-\hat{c}_{oi}) + \mathbf{R}^o \dot{c}_i = \dot{p}_i \quad (4)$$

where $\omega = \dot{\theta}$ is the angular velocity of the object and the hat operator for a vector $v = [v_x \ v_y \ v_z]^T$ in the planar case is defined as $\hat{v} \triangleq [v_y \ -v_x \ 0]^T$. Therefore (4) can be written as

$$\mathbf{J}_{oi} \dot{p} + v_{ri} = \mathbf{J}_{vi} \dot{q}_i \quad (5)$$

where $p = [x \ y \ z \ \theta]^T$ denotes the object's pose, q_i denote the joint position vector for arm i , $\mathbf{J}_{oi} = [\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \ -\hat{c}_{oi}]$, \mathbf{J}_{vi} is the translation part of the i th arm's Jacobian and $v_{ri} = \mathbf{R}^o \dot{c}_i$ denotes the sliding velocity of the contact point with respect to the object.

The proposed control scheme consists of two stages. The control objective of the first stage is to reach a desired object orientation while the objective of the second stage is to reach the desired position maintaining the desired orientation already reached in the first stage. For the first stage, contact

sliding on the object surface is allowed whereas in the second stage contacts should remain fixed. We can express these motion constraints in the velocity level by setting in (5) $\dot{x}_{ci} = 0$ for the first stage and ${}^o \dot{c}_i$ equal to 0 for the second stage. Thus we get the velocity constraints:

$$\dot{\phi}_{ni} = \mathbf{n}_{xi}^T (\mathbf{J}_{vi} \dot{q}_i - \mathbf{J}_{oi} \dot{p}) = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_{ti} = \mathbf{t}_{yi}^T (\mathbf{J}_{vi} \dot{q}_i - \mathbf{J}_{oi} \dot{p}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

where the normal and tangential vectors to the contacted surface are given by $\mathbf{n}_{xi} = (-1)^{i+1} \mathbf{R} [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, $\mathbf{t}_{yi} = (-1)^{i+1} \mathbf{R} [0 \ 1 \ 0]^T$. Our aim is to enforce the respective constraints at each stage by a suitable control input. In particular, constraint (6) must be satisfied in the first stage and both (6), (7) must be satisfied in the second stage. We can write the constraint equations (6), (7) in compact form for each arm and for each stage as follows:

$$\dot{\Phi} = [{}^s D_r \quad {}^s D_o] \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \\ \dot{p} \end{bmatrix} = 0, \quad s = \{1, 2\} \quad (8)$$

where for the first stage:

$${}^1 D_r = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_{x1}^T \mathbf{J}_{v1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{n}_{x2}^T \mathbf{J}_{v2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$${}^1 D_o = -[\mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{n}_{x1} \quad \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{n}_{x2}]^T \quad (10)$$

and for the second stage:

$${}^2 D_r = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_{x1}^T \mathbf{J}_{v1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{n}_{x2}^T \mathbf{J}_{v2} \\ \mathbf{t}_{y1}^T \mathbf{J}_{v1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{t}_{y2}^T \mathbf{J}_{v2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$${}^2 D_o = -[\mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{n}_{x1} \quad \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{n}_{x2} \quad \mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{t}_{y1} \quad \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{t}_{y2}]^T \quad (12)$$

The dynamics of both n dof arms with gravity compensation and the object can be compactly written as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\xi} + \mathbf{C} \dot{\xi} + {}^s D^T s \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{F}_{fr} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u} \quad (13)$$

where $\xi = [q_1^T \ q_2^T \ p^T]^T$ is the system's position vector, $\mathbf{M} = \text{blockdiag}(\mathbf{M}_1(q_1), \mathbf{M}_2(q_2), \mathbf{M}_o)$ with $\mathbf{M}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ the inertia matrices of each arm and $\mathbf{M}_o = \text{blockdiag}(m_o \mathbf{I}_3, I_{oz}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ the object inertia matrix with m_o the object mass and I_{zo} the inertia of the object around axis z . $\mathbf{C} = \text{blockdiag}(\mathbf{C}_1(q_1, \dot{q}_1), \mathbf{C}_2(q_2, \dot{q}_2), \mathbf{0}_{4 \times 4})$ where $\mathbf{C}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the Coriolis and centrifugal forces matrix for each arm. With $\text{blockdiag}(\cdot)$ we denote a block diagonal matrix. The control input $\mathbf{u} = [u_1^T \ u_2^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ is applied through $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{I}_{2n} \ \mathbf{0}_{2n \times 4}]^T$, the constraint matrix is ${}^s D = [{}^s D_r \quad {}^s D_o]$ and the constraint forces are ${}^1 \mathbf{f} = [f_{n1} \ f_{n2}]^T$ and ${}^2 \mathbf{f} = [f_{n1} \ f_{n2} \ f_{t1} \ f_{t2}]^T$. Normal forces f_{ni} are associated with the interaction forces between the robotic arms and the object. Notice that $f_{ni} > 0$ is a sufficient condition for the satisfaction of constraint (6), maintaining the contact between the arms and the object. Tangential forces f_{ti} are associated with the satisfaction of

constraint (7) and are physically attributed to the friction between the arms and the object. Thus by applying appropriate normal forces, constraint (7) can be successfully enforced. Vector $\mathbf{F}_{fr} = [\mathbf{0} \quad \mathbf{0} \quad \mathbf{f}_{fr}^T]^T$ denotes the friction between the object and the supporting surface. Therefore the system for the first stage is described by (13) with (9) and (10) and for the second stage by (13) with (11) and (12).

Proposition 1. *Control input \mathbf{u} and output $\dot{\mathbf{q}} = [\dot{\mathbf{q}}_1^T \quad \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2^T]^T$ form a passive pair.*

Proof. Multiplying the first two sets of equations of (13) with $\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T$ we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{u} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}_r \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{C}_r \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{D}_r^T \mathbf{f} \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbf{M}_r = \text{blockdiag}(\mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_2)$, $\mathbf{C}_r = \text{blockdiag}(\mathbf{C}_1, \mathbf{C}_2)$. Using (9) (11), (10) (12), (5), $\mathbf{v}_{ri}^T \mathbf{n}_{xi} = 0$ for both stages, and $\mathbf{v}_{ri}^T \mathbf{t}_{yi} = 0$ for the second stage, the last term of (14) is written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{D}_r^T \mathbf{f} = -\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{D}_o \mathbf{f} \quad (15)$$

Thus (14) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}_r \dot{\mathbf{q}}) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{D}_o \mathbf{f} \quad (16)$$

Multiplying the last set of equations of (13) with $\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T$ we get:

$$-\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{D}_o \mathbf{f} = \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{M}_o \ddot{\mathbf{p}} + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} (\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{M}_o \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} \quad (17)$$

Substituting (17) to (16) we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}_r \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{M}_o \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} \quad (18)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} > 0$ due to the dissipative nature of friction forces. Thus Proposition 1 has been proven. \square

III. PROPOSED CONTROL INPUT

As explained at the end of Section I, the control strategy consists of two stages. The objective of the first stage is twofold. The object must be rotated to the desired orientation, while the bimanual robot remains in contact with it at all time, satisfying equation (6). During the second stage, the object must be displaced to the desired position, while maintaining the orientation reached at the end of the first stage, with the robotic arms remaining in contact and not moving relative to the object satisfying equations (6), (7). The control input will be designed to drive the state to an equilibrium manifold that accomplishes the control objectives, while preserving the system passivity. We draw inspiration from previous works which utilize passivity tools to design controllers for grasping and in-hand manipulation of a rectangular object by two fingers with rolling spherical tips in gravity free environment [29]–[31]. In these works the superposition of separately designed control inputs is able to achieve the overall task.

We will initially derive the object equilibrium conditions. In the object dynamics, setting $\ddot{\mathbf{p}} = \dot{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{0}$ we get ${}^s \mathbf{D}_o^T \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{0}$. For the first stage this implies:

$$\mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{n}_{x1} f_{n1} + \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{n}_{x2} f_{n2} = \mathbf{0} \quad (19)$$

using $\mathbf{J}_{oi}^T \mathbf{n}_{xi} = (-1)^{i+1} [\mathbf{n}_{xo}^T \quad -y_{ci}]^T$, where \mathbf{n}_{xo} is the first column of \mathbf{R} , (19) is written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_{xo}(f_{n1} - f_{n2}) \\ -f_{n1}y_{c1} + f_{n2}y_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (20)$$

which implies the equilibrium conditions:

$$f_{n1} = f_{n2} \quad (21)$$

$$y_{c1} - y_{c2} = 0 \quad (22)$$

These conditions define the equilibrium manifold for the first stage where (21) implies that the arms apply equal and opposing normal forces to the object and (22) implies that these forces are applied along the interaction line $\mathbf{c}_2 - \mathbf{c}_1$. For the second stage we get:

$$\mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{n}_{x1} f_{n1} + \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{n}_{x2} f_{n2} + \mathbf{J}_{o1}^T \mathbf{n}_{y1} f_{t1} + \mathbf{J}_{o2}^T \mathbf{t}_{y2} f_{n2} = \mathbf{0} \quad (23)$$

which using $\mathbf{J}_{oi}^T \mathbf{t}_{yi} = (-1)^{i+1} [\mathbf{t}_{yo}^T \quad x_{ci}]^T$, where \mathbf{t}_{yo} is the second column of \mathbf{R} , (23) can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_{xo}(f_{n2} - f_{n1}) + \mathbf{t}_{yo}(f_{t2} - f_{t1}) \\ -f_{n1}y_{c1} + f_{n2}y_{c2} + f_{t1}x_{c1} - f_{t2}x_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (24)$$

Since \mathbf{n}_{xo} , \mathbf{t}_{yo} are orthogonal, and $x_{c2} - x_{c1} = l$, (24) implies again (21) and:

$$f_{t1} = f_{t2} \quad (25)$$

$$l f_{t1} + f_{n1}(y_{c1} - y_{c2}) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Notice that if $y_{c1} - y_{c2} = 0$, (25), (26) implies:

$$f_{t1} = f_{t2} = 0 \quad (27)$$

For the first stage starting with the end-effectors in contact with the object we propose the following control signal to achieve a point in the equilibrium manifold (21), (22):

$${}^1 \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{g1} + \mathbf{u}_{r1} + \mathbf{u}_{q1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{g2} + \mathbf{u}_{r2} + \mathbf{u}_{q2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\mathbf{u}_{gi} = \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{f}_{di} + \mathbf{u}_{mi}) \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{ri} = \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{u}_{\theta i} \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{qi} = -\mathbf{K}_{vi} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i \quad (31)$$

with

$$\mathbf{f}_{di} = (-1)^{i+1} f_d \mathbf{e}_1 \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{mi} = (-1)^{i+1} \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l} f_d \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (33)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\theta i} = (-1)^{i+1} k_\theta \left((\theta - \theta_d) + \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l} \right) \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (34)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_1 = [1 \quad 0 \quad 0]^T$, $\mathbf{e}_2 = [0 \quad 1 \quad 0]^T$, $f_d > 0$ is the desired force to be applied to the object sides, θ_d is the desired rotation angle k_θ is a positive gain and \mathbf{K}_{vi} a diagonal matrix of positive gains. The purpose of (31) is to ensure that the joint velocities of redundant robots are driven to zero as the control objective is reached.

For the second stage starting at the equilibrium manifold of the first stage (21), (22) we propose the following control

signal to achieve a point in the equilibrium manifold (21), (22), (27):

$${}^2\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{g1} + \mathbf{u}_{r1} + \mathbf{u}_{q1} + \mathbf{u}_{x1} + \mathbf{u}_{y1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{g2} + \mathbf{u}_{r2} + \mathbf{u}_{q2} + \mathbf{u}_{x2} + \mathbf{u}_{y2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

where \mathbf{u}_{gi} , \mathbf{u}_{ri} and \mathbf{u}_{qi} are given by (29), (30) and (31) and:

$$\mathbf{u}_{xi} = -\mathbf{J}_{vi}^T (k_x (x - x_d) + d_x \dot{x}) \mathbf{e}_1 \quad (36)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{yi} = -\mathbf{J}_{vi}^T (k_y (y - y_d) + d_y \dot{y}) \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (37)$$

with k_x, d_x, k_y, d_y positive gains and x_d, y_d the desired object position.

IV. STABILITY ANALYSIS

Lemma 1. *The following equality holds $\forall u_x, u_y \in \mathbb{R}$:*

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = ({}^o\dot{x} - \dot{\theta} y_{ci}) u_x + ({}^o\dot{y} + \dot{\theta} x_{ci} + \dot{y}_{ci}) u_y \quad (38)$$

where ${}^o\dot{x}, {}^o\dot{y}$ is the object body velocity.

Proof. Using (5), the left side of (38) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = (\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{J}_{oi} \dot{\mathbf{p}} + {}^o\mathbf{v}_{ri})^T \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Substituting \mathbf{J}_{oi} and \mathbf{v}_{ri} (39) implies:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \left(\begin{bmatrix} {}^o\dot{x} - \dot{\theta} y_{ci} \\ {}^o\dot{y} + \dot{\theta} x_{ci} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{y}_{ci} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right)^T \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

which is equal to the right hand side of (38). \square

Theorem 1. *Control input (28) in system (13), (9), (10) achieves the asymptotic convergence of θ to θ_d , $y_{c2} - y_{c1}$ to 0 and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ to $\mathbf{0}$.*

Proof. Multiplying control input (31) with $\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T$ we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{q1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{q2} \end{bmatrix} = -\dot{\mathbf{q}}_1^T \mathbf{K}_{v1} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_1 - \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2^T \mathbf{K}_{v2} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2 = -\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{K}_v \dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (41)$$

For (29) we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{g1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{g2} \end{bmatrix} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}_1^T \mathbf{J}_{v1}^T \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{f}_{d1} + \mathbf{u}_{m1}) + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2^T \mathbf{J}_{v2}^T \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{f}_{d2} + \mathbf{u}_{m2}) \quad (42)$$

using Lemma 1 for $u_x = f_d$ (32) and $u_y = f_d \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l}$, (33) and $x_{c2} - x_{c1} = l$, (42) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{g1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{g2} \end{bmatrix} = \dot{\theta} (y_{c2} - y_{c1}) f_d - (l\dot{\theta} + \dot{y}_{c2} - \dot{y}_{c1}) f_d \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l} \quad (43)$$

which implies:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{g1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{g2} \end{bmatrix} = -(\dot{y}_{c2} - \dot{y}_{c1}) f_d \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l} = -\dot{V}_g \quad (44)$$

where

$$V_g = \frac{f_d}{2l} (y_{c2} - y_{c1})^2 \quad (45)$$

Thus $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ and $[\mathbf{u}_{g1}^T \quad \mathbf{u}_{g2}^T]^T$ is a passive pair. Repeating the same process for (30) we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{r1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{r2} \end{bmatrix} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}_1^T \mathbf{J}_{v1}^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{u}_{\theta 1} + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2^T \mathbf{J}_{v2}^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{u}_{\theta 2} \quad (46)$$

using Lemma 1 for $u_x = 0$ and $u_y = \kappa_\theta (\theta - \theta_d + \frac{y_{c2} - y_{c1}}{l})$, (34) and $x_{c2} - x_{c1} = l$, (46) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{r1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{r2} \end{bmatrix} = -\dot{V}_r \quad (47)$$

where

$$V_r = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} y_{c2} - y_{c1} \\ \theta - \theta_d \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\kappa_\theta}{l} & \kappa_\theta \\ \kappa_\theta & l\kappa_\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{c2} - y_{c1} \\ \theta - \theta_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (48)$$

Substituting (41), (44), (47) in (18) we get:

$$-\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{K}_v \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \dot{V}_g - \dot{V}_r = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}_r \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{M}_o \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} \quad (49)$$

Thus we can select the candidate Lyapunov-like function:

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}_r \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{M}_o \dot{\mathbf{p}} + \delta^T \mathbf{A} \delta) \quad (50)$$

where $\delta = [y_{c2} - y_{c1} \quad \theta - \theta_d]^T$ and $\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\kappa_\theta + f_d}{l} & \kappa_\theta \\ \kappa_\theta & l\kappa_\theta \end{bmatrix}$.

Notice that \mathbf{A} is positive definite. Then using (49) we get:

$$\dot{V}_1 = -\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{K}_v \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{f}_{fr} \quad (51)$$

which means that $V_1(t) \leq V_1(0)$, implying that $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$ are bounded. However by noticing that ${}^1\mathbf{f}$ in (13), (28) can be written as a function of bounded quantities we can conclude that \dot{V} is bounded and thus \dot{V} is uniformly continuous which implies the convergence of $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$ to $\mathbf{0}$. Using function convergence arguments we can show that $\ddot{\xi}$ also converges to zero and thus the object is at an equilibrium state. As explained in Section III at equilibrium, (21) and (22) hold, thus $y_{c2} - y_{c1} = 0$ and $\theta = \theta_d$. \square

Lemma 2. *In the second stage, the following equality holds $\forall u_x, u_y$:*

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \dot{x} u_x + \dot{y} u_y \quad (52)$$

Proof. Assuming that in the second stage $\theta = \theta_d$ and $y_{c2} - y_{c1} = 0 \forall t$, $\dot{\theta} = 0$, $\mathbf{v}_{ri} = \mathbf{0}$. Using (5) and substituting \mathbf{J}_{oi} as well as $\mathbf{v}_{ri} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0$ the left side of (52) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T [\mathbf{I}_3 \quad -\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{oi}] \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (53)$$

which is equal to the right hand side of (52). \square

Theorem 2. *Control input (35) in system (13), (11), (12) achieves the asymptotic convergence of x to x_d , y to y_d and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ to $\mathbf{0}$ assuming $\theta = \theta_d$, $y_{c2} - y_{c1} = 0 \forall t$.*

Proof. Multiplying the sum of (36) and (37) with $\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T$ we get:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{x1} + \mathbf{u}_{y1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{x2} + \mathbf{u}_{y2} \end{bmatrix} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}_1^T \mathbf{J}_{v1}^T (\mathbf{u}_{x1} + \mathbf{u}_{y1}) + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_2^T \mathbf{J}_{v2}^T (\mathbf{u}_{x2} + \mathbf{u}_{y2}) \quad (54)$$

which using Lemma 2 with $u_x = -(k_x(x - x_d) + d_x \dot{x})$ and $u_y = -(k_y(y - y_d) + d_y \dot{y})$ implies:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{x1} + \mathbf{u}_{y1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{x2} + \mathbf{u}_{y2} \end{bmatrix} &= -2\dot{x}(k_x(x - x_d) + d_x \dot{x}) - \\ 2\dot{y}(k_y(y - y_d) + d_y \dot{y}) &= -\dot{V}_x - 2d_x \dot{x}^2 - \dot{V}_y - 2d_y \dot{y}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

where

$$V_x = k_x(x - x_d)^2 \quad (56)$$

$$V_y = k_y(y - y_d)^2 \quad (57)$$

Following the same process as in the proof of Theorem 1 we select the candidate Lyapunov-like function:

$$V_2 = V_1 + V_x + V_y \quad (58)$$

and by taking its derivative we get:

$$\dot{V}_2 = \dot{V}_1 - 2d_x \dot{x}^2 - 2d_y \dot{y}^2 \quad (59)$$

Following the same line of proof of Theorem 1, we can prove that \dot{V}_2 , and thus $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$, \dot{x} , \dot{y} converge to zero as well as $\ddot{\xi}$. This implies that the system is at an equilibrium state. Following the results of Section III, it is easy to show that x converges to x_d and that y converges to y_d . \square

Remark 1. Ensuring that the contact points remain constant in the second stage can be achieved by leveraging the friction forces between the robotic arms and the object. When the tangent forces remain inside the friction cone then the static friction will not allow sliding motion of the end-effectors. Tangent forces are generated from control inputs (36) and (37). By selecting a large enough value for f_d it can be ensured that contact forces remain within the friction cone. In that case since $y_{c2} - y_{c1} \equiv 0$ the object is not subjected to any rotating moment, which implies $\dot{\theta} \equiv 0$.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to perform more realistic simulations of the system, we will model the friction forces between the object and the supporting surface using the elastoplastic friction model [32]. This model has been proposed for modelling friction in one dimension and it has been successfully utilized in robotics applications [16]. Details on the elastoplastic friction model can be found in the Appendix. To simulate the constraints (8), the Baumgarte method [33] was used.

In our theoretical analysis we did not elaborate on the friction model. When the contact area is large, like in our case, static friction forces may hinder the closed loop system to converge to θ_d , x_d , y_d . To remedy this situation, we added in $\mathbf{u}_{\theta i}$ (30), $\mathbf{u}_{x i}$ (36), $\mathbf{u}_{y i}$ (37) the following integral control terms $\kappa_{I\theta} \int (\theta - \theta_d) dt$, $\kappa_{Ix} \int (x - x_d) dt$ and $\kappa_{Iy} \int (y - y_d) dt$ respectively. However, the presence of the integrator in $\mathbf{u}_{\theta i}$, implies that at steady state $y_{c2} - y_{c1} = -\frac{I\kappa_{I\theta}}{f_d + \kappa_\theta} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int (\theta - \theta_d) dt$. However, $y_{c2} - y_{c1} \equiv 0$ is

Fig. 2: Simulation Result: Object pose at the beginning (upper left), end of the first stage stage (upper right), end of the transition stage (bottom left), end of the second stage (bottom right)

required in the second stage as stated by Theorem 2. Thus we implemented a transition stage, where the integrator is continuously driven to 0 using a first order system.

We simulated the system with a bimanual planar robot with two 3 dof arms with revolute joints, manipulating a rectangular object with dimensions $0.4m \times 0.3m$ weighing $10kg$. We used damping $10N/rad^2$ for each joint and set $f_d = 35N$, $\kappa_\theta = 80$, $\kappa_x = \kappa_y = 200$, $d_x = d_y = 20$, $\kappa_{I\theta} = 20$, $\kappa_{Ix} = \kappa_{Iy} = 30$. In Figure 2 the initial pose of the box and its pose at the end of each stage is depicted together with the contact points demonstrating the achievement of each stage's goal. This can be further shown in Figures 3 and 4 where the response of the object's pose and of the term $y_{c2} - y_{c1}$ are shown respectively. The vertical lines denote the end of each stage. The object successfully reaches the desired orientation, then $y_{c2} - y_{c1}$ is driven to zero and finally the object reaches the desired position overcoming the friction. Finally in Figure 5 the normal and tangential forces are shown. By taking the maximum value of $\frac{f_{t1}(t)}{f_{n1}(t)}$ and $\frac{f_{t2}(t)}{f_{n2}(t)}$ during the second stage, which corresponds to contact force angles of 14.2° and 33.5° , we conclude that the end effector contacts will remain fixed and not slide for the typical 45° friction cone that holds for the vast majority of materials in contact. Notice that the normal forces do not converge to f_d , nor the tangential to 0, rather to a displaced value depending on the final values of the integrators of $x - x_d$ and $y - y_d$.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To validate the proposed approach we implemented the controller using two KUKA LBR iiwa 7 robots under gravity compensation, driven at the torque level at $500Hz$. The software runs on a real-time Linux PC, using the FRI library to communicate with the robot. To get visual feedback an Intel RealSense D435i RGBD sensor is used, tracking an April tag at the geometric center of the object. The controller is communicating with the vision sensor using ROS. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 6. The control scheme utilized in Section V was also utilized in the experiments.

Fig. 3: Simulation Result: Object position and orientation

Fig. 4: Simulation Result: Contact points y coordinate difference

Fig. 5: Simulation Result: Normal and tangential forces applied to the object

Fig. 6: Experimental Setup

To facilitate the application of forces normal to the surface, an orientation tracking controller is used [34] to keep the end-effectors of the robots normal to the object sides.

We performed experiments using three objects, a 0.26×0.36 box containing biscuits, weighing $4kg$, a 0.4×0.48 piece of luggage weighing $15kg$ and a 0.23×0.35 box weighing $11.5kg$, filled in the left half with books and in the right half with foam, to have an object with largely uneven mass distribution. We conducted multiple experiments with different initial and goal poses with all three objects, with the control scheme being able to reach the desired pose in all cases. The controller parameters were set equal to $10N/rad^2$ damping for each joint, $f_d = 55N$, $\kappa_\theta = 150$, $\kappa_x = \kappa_y = 400$, $d_x = d_y = 280$, $\kappa_{I\theta} = 15$, $\kappa_{Ix} = \kappa_{Iy} = 10$.

Experimental results for one execution of the biscuit box are shown in Figures 7 - 10. In Figure 7 the object is shown after the successful execution of each stage, which is verified in Figure 8 depicting the position response and in Figure 9 depicting $y_{c2} - y_{c1}$. The small errors in $y_{c2} - y_{c1}$ in the end of the transition stage are attributed to the friction between the object and the robotic arms without affecting the system performance as shown in Figure 8. In Figure 10 the normal and tangential forces are shown. As in the simulations, there is a small error in the convergence of normal and tangential forces attributed to the integrators. Notice the existence of non zero tangential forces during the first stage which can be attributed to the friction between the end-effectors and the object as opposed to the simulation results.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

A control scheme is proposed and successfully implemented, achieving bimanual manipulation of large objects supported on planar surfaces. The control scheme rotates the object to a desired orientation and then translates it to the desired position. During the task execution the controller ensures that the bimanual robot remains in contact with the object. Simulation and experimental results using a bimanual robot with two KUKA LBR iiwa 7 manipulators show successful object manipulation, using a variety of objects.

Fig. 7: Experimental Result: Object pose at the beginning (upper left), end of the first stage (upper right), end of the transition stage (bottom left), end of the second stage (bottom right)

Fig. 8: Experimental Result: Object position and orientation

Fig. 9: Experimental Result: Contact points y coordinate difference

Fig. 10: Experimental Result: Normal and tangential forces applied to the object

APPENDIX: THE ELASTOPLASTIC FRICTION MODEL

To model planar motion with the elastoplastic model we will utilize the coupling of translational and rotational friction [35] using the notion of frictional limit surfaces [36], [37]. According to this model, the planar friction $\mathbf{f}_{fr} = [f_x \ f_y \ f_\theta]^T$ lies upon the elliptic surface:

$$\mathbf{f}_{fr}^T \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(\mu f_N)^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{(\mu f_N)^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(\alpha R \mu f_N)^2} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{fr} = 1 \quad (60)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient, f_N is the normal to the surface force, α is parameter that is experimentally calculated equal to $\alpha \approx 0.63$ and R is related to the contact area between the two objects. According to the elastoplastic friction model, the displacement and rotation \mathbf{p} during motion under friction is the sum of an elastic part \mathbf{z} and a plastic part \mathbf{w} . The value of the friction force is given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_{fr} = \Sigma_0 \mathbf{z} + \Sigma_1 \dot{\mathbf{z}} + \Sigma_2 \dot{\mathbf{p}} \quad (61)$$

where Σ_i are diagonal positive matrices and:

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \left(\mathbf{I} - \text{diag}(\mathbf{z}) \text{diag}(\mathbf{z}_{ss})^{-1} \text{diag}(\alpha(\mathbf{z}, \dot{\mathbf{p}}, \mathbf{z}_{ba})) \right) \dot{\mathbf{p}} \quad (62)$$

where $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denotes a diagonal matrix with its elements being the components of the argument vector. The variable $\alpha(\mathbf{z}, \dot{\mathbf{p}}, \mathbf{z}_{ba})$ facilitates the transition from static to kinetic friction and for each of its components holds $\forall i = \{x, y, \theta\}$:

$$\alpha_i = \begin{cases} 0, & |z_i| \leq z_{bai} \\ \frac{1}{2} \sin\left(\frac{z_i - \frac{z_{ssi} + z_{bai}}{2}}{z_{ssi} - z_{bai}}\right) + \frac{1}{2}, & z_{bai} < |z_i| < z_{ssi} \\ 1, & |z_i| \geq z_{ssi} \end{cases} \quad (63)$$

for $z_i \dot{p}_i > 0$ and $\alpha_i = 0$ for $z_i \dot{p}_i \leq 0$. The maximum value of the elastic displacement is given by:

$$\mathbf{z}_{ss} = \begin{cases} \Sigma_0^{-1} \mathbf{g}_{max}, & \|\dot{\mathbf{p}}\| = 0 \\ \Sigma_0^{-1} \mathbf{g}(\dot{\mathbf{p}}), & \|\dot{\mathbf{p}}\| > 0 \end{cases} \quad (64)$$

where $\mathbf{g}_{max} = [\mu_S f_N \quad \mu_S f_N \quad \alpha R \mu_S f_N]^T$, with μ_S the static friction coefficient. The Stribeck curve $\mathbf{g}(\dot{\mathbf{p}})$ is:

$$\mathbf{g}(\dot{\mathbf{p}}) = \left(\mathbf{I} + \left(\frac{\mu_S}{\mu_C} - 1 \right) \exp(-v) \right) \frac{\mathbf{A}_C^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{p}}}{\sqrt{\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{A}_C^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{p}}}} \quad (65)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = \left[\frac{\dot{p}_x^2}{V_S^2} \quad \frac{\dot{p}_y^2}{V_S^2} \quad \frac{\omega^2}{\Omega_S} \right]^T$ with V_S, Ω_S being the Stribeck translational and angular velocity constants, μ_C is the kinetic friction coefficient and \mathbf{A}_C is given by the matrix of (60) setting $\mu = \mu_C$. The breakaway elastic displacement is:

$$\mathbf{z}_{ba} = \frac{\mathbf{A}_{ba}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{p}}}{\sqrt{\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{A}_{ba}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{p}}}} \quad (66)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{ba} = \text{diag} \left(\left[\frac{1}{f_{ba}^2} \quad \frac{1}{f_{ba}^2} \quad \frac{1}{(\alpha R f_{ba})^2} \right] \right)$, with f_{ba} denoting the constant breakaway force. For more information on the elastoplastic model the reader is referred to [16], [32].

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